

Ayurvedic Herbal Formulations for Detoxification

¹R.Ramasubramania Raja*, ²S.Sriram, ³M.Gopal Rao

⁴S.Sivaprakash, ⁴J.Shivani, ⁴V.Vrindha, ⁴R.Anamika, ⁴T.Senthilnathan

¹Asst.Professor (Asso.Grade) College of Pharmacy, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Coimbatore.

²Principal, College of Pharmacy, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Coimbatore.

³Vice Principal, College of Pharmacy, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Coimbatore.

⁴Sixth Sem B.Pharm, College of Pharmacy, Sri Ramakrishna Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Coimbatore.

*Corresponding author Email: rsmr.raj1979@gmail.com

Abstract:

Detoxification is designed to reduce the damage done to the body by drugs. This is done by removing foreign substances from the blood in the liver, where all toxins are processed and removed. The body also removes toxins through the kidneys, intestines, lungs, lymphatic system and skin. The body also removes toxins through the kidneys, intestines, lungs, lymphatic system and skin. However, when these systems are affected, foreign substances cannot be filtered properly and the body is affected. Follow the diet and daily routine for our mind-body type and imbalances; exercise every day to improve our digestion and elimination; do a daily abhyanga to flush out toxins through the skin; drink the herbal water suitable for our imbalances; and meditate every day to remove stress.

Keywords: Detoxification, intestines, kidneys, lymphatic, abhayanga, herbal water

Introduction:

Detoxification is a set of interventions designed to control intoxication and withdrawal. It represents the removal of toxins from the body of seriously ill patients and/or medical products. Detoxification is designed to reduce the damage done to the body by drugs. This is done by removing foreign substances from the blood in the liver, where all toxins are processed and removed. The body also removes toxins through the kidneys, intestines, lungs, lymphatic system and skin. Detox involves relaxing, cleansing and caring for the body from the inside out. It involves removing and eliminating toxins from the body and then providing healthy nutrients. Detoxification can help we fight disease and improve our ability to maintain our health through a variety of methods including yoga, meditation and other practices recommended by Ayurveda. Detox means cleansing the blood. This is done by removing impurities from the blood in the liver, where all toxins are processed to be removed. The body also removes toxins through the kidney

ys,intestines, lungs, lymphatic system and skin. However, when these systems are affected, foreign substances cannot be filtered properly and the body is affected. Follow the diet and daily routine for our mind-body type and imbalances; exercise every day to improve our digestion and elimination; do a daily abhyanga to flush out toxins through the skin; drink the herbal water suitable for our imbalances; and meditate every day to remove stress.(Agnivesh *et al* 2001)

Triphala:

Triphala is known for its mild laxative properties that help support healthy digestion and elimination. This herb, made up of three fruits, is important in Ayurvedic practice and helps cleanse and detoxify the digestive system.

Turmeric:

Turmeric is a yellow spice that contains curcumin, a powerful antioxidant with anti-inflammatory properties. In addition to its culinary properties, turmeric supports liver function and plays an important role in the detoxification process. It has been included in Ayurvedic recipes for its general health benefits.

Neem:

Known for its purifying and bloodpurifying properties, Neem is a versatile plant in Ayurveda. It actively supports the body's detoxification mechanisms. It can also be used in skin care products due to its ability to keep the skin healthy.

Guduchi:

Guduchi is known as a rejuvenating herb that helps strengthen the immune system and promotes the elimination of toxins from the body. Guduchi is often used in conjunction with other herbs and plays an important role in Ayurvedic detoxification practices.

Amla (Indian Gooseberry):

Amla is rich in vitamin C and antioxidants that support liver function and help eliminate toxins. It helps in detoxification as well as improving overall immunity, making it an important ingredient in the Ayurvedic diet.

Fenugreek:

Fenugreek seeds have antiinflammatory properties and support liver and kidney function. Ayurvedic foods often include fenugreek for its digestive benefits.

Panchakarma and its benefits for detoxification

Ayurveda uses holistic detoxification treatments in addition to using herbs alone. Panchakarma is a prominent example. Panchakarma is an ancient Ayurvedic treatment that has been proven effective in removing toxins from the body, thus improving physical and mental health. This therapy has measurable blood metabolites associated with inflammation, cardiovascular risk, and cholesterol control. Panchakarma, an important detoxification treatment, is an effective method with many benefits that resolve internal diseases and improve overall health. According to its idea, it is to create harmony in the body. As people increasingly seek natural remedies for health, Ayurveda, with its emphasis on detoxification through herbs, continues to gain traction and recognition for its ability to promote equality and healing. Itoozhi Ayurveda is one of the renowned Ayurvedic clinics in Kerala, focusing specifically on lifestyle diseases and eye treatments.

Ayurvedic herbs for natural detoxification**1. Triphala (Three Fruits)**

This classic Ayurvedic recipe combines three powerful fruits: amla (Indian gooseberry), haritaki, and bibhitaki. *Trichosanthes* stimulates bowel movements, helps eliminate waste, and acts as a mild laxative. It is known for its detoxifying properties that promote internal cleansing and rejuvenation.

2. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*)

Turmeric is known for its antiinflammatory and antioxidant properties and is an important ingredient in Ayurvedic medicine. Curcumin, the active compound in turmeric, supports liver function, the body's main detoxification system. It helps eliminate toxins and improve overall health.

3. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*)

Neem is a plant with powerful detoxifying and purifying properties. It helps cleanse the blood, strengthen the immune system, and rid the body of harmful bacteria. Neem is often used to support healthy skin, which is an important part of overall detoxification.

4. Guduchi (*Tinospora cordifolia*)

Also known as 'Amrit', meaning nectar of the gods, guduchi is valued for its antiinflammatory and detoxifying properties. It helps in purifying the blood, strengthening the heart and enhancing the body's natural defense mechanisms.

5. Cilantro (*Coriandrum sativum*)

Coriander is a popular herb in Ayurveda known for its ability to chelate heavy metals in the body. It supports the body's detoxification process, especially the removal of toxins like mercury. Incorporating these Ayurvedic remedies into our daily life, along with a healthy diet and lifestyle, can help ensure a healthy and productive life. However, it is important to consult a qualified physician or Ayurvedic practitioner before making any major changes to our health, especially if we have an underlying medical condition or are taking medications. Adopting the Ayurvedic philosophy can be a gentle and holistic way to support our body's detoxification process and improve our overall health.

Ayurvedic detoxification is based primarily on the long-established prescriptions of Ayurvedic medicine. (Vagbhata *et al* 2005)

Ayurveda divides the world into five

elements: Vayu (air), Prithvi (earth), Teja (fire), Aakash (space), and Jala (water).

It is believed that different combinations of each element form three fluids, also known as doshas, which are responsible for various physiological functions of the body.

The three doshas are Vata, Kapha, and Pitta. To ensure proper health, the three doshas and the five elements must be balanced. Any imbalance is said to result in disease. An imbalance in waste products (Mutra (urine), Purisha (stool), and Sweda (sweat)) is also known to cause diseases such as diarrhea, constipation, asthma, arthritis, skin problems, and urinary tract infections. Detoxification should be a regular part of rebalancing our health. Remember that each person has a unique dosha balance based on genetic and personality traits that are associated with various health outcomes. An Ayurvedic doctor can help to identify our dosha and the

appropriate treatment options. Some Ayurvedic sources recommend a detox at the beginning of each season to remove toxins that may have accumulated in the previous season due to food, stress, and other factors. The steps and practices of Ayurvedic detox

Not all Ayurvedic detoxes are the same, as people have different doshas, but all detoxes are said to remove impurities and toxins from the body. In addition to detoxifying our body, we are also encouraged to make comprehensive diet and lifestyle changes to restore energy balance.

Bodily detox (Purvakarma and Panchakarma)

The first stage, called Purvakarma, is designed to move toxins into our intestines and skin so they can be eliminated from the body. To improve mental health, a more intensive treatment called Panchakarma is then recommended to rejuvenate the body and improve detoxification.

It has five karmas (cures)

1. Virechan: Wash using powder, paste or heated herbs
2. Vaman: Vomiting or laxatives
3. Basti: Massage and enema using warm oil
4. Rakta moksha: Detoxification of the blood, also known as bloodletting
5. Nasya: Nasal Cleansing Using herbs, oils, and tobacco

Proponents say the goal of Panchakarma is not just to remove toxins, but to restore harmony between mind and body. Most people who undergo Ayurvedic detox also take herbs, medications, and teas to cleanse their bodies and bowels. These can take the form of herbal cleanses, detox products, enemas, and bowel stimulants.

Sexual intercourse and bowel movement. Dietary modification.

Although each dosha requires a different diet, we are supposed to avoid any foods that are believed to cause toxin buildup in our body. These include alcohol, caffeine, artificial sweeteners, red meat, and processed foods

Dosha	Foods to eat	Foods to avoid
Pitta	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sweet, energizing, cold foods • bitter foods • sweet fruit • non-starchy vegetables • dairy • eggs • barley • oats • basmati or white rice • wheat • legumes • some spices (e.g., cardamom, turmeric, cinnamon, cilantro, mint) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • spicy, acidic, hot foods • sour foods • red meats (limit other animal products) • potatoes • eggplant • tomatoes • nuts • seeds • dried fruit • lentils
Kapha	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • spicy and acidic foods • most fruits (e.g., apples, cherries, mangos, peaches, raisins, pears) • most vegetables (especially cruciferous or “bitter” vegetables) • barley • corn • millet • basmati rice • low fat dairy • eggs • chicken • turkey • rabbit • legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • heavy, fatty foods • nuts • seeds • fats and oils (e.g., ghee, butter, vegetable oils) • white beans • black lentils

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • all spices 	
Vata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “warm,” “moist,” and easily digested foods • sweet fruits (e.g., berries, bananas, apples, figs, coconut, grapefruit, mangoes, oranges, peaches, pineapple, etc.) • soft, easily digested vegetables (e.g., asparagus, sweet potato, leafy greens) • oats, • brown rice, • wheat, • most lean meats and eggs, • dairy (buttermilk, yogurt, cheese, ghee, whole milk), • nuts, • seeds, • most spices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dried and bitter fruits • raw vegetables • beans, lentils • limit chili pepper and other hot spices

Water should be our main drink during the detox. Ginger tea also supports its stomach-soothing properties. In general, we should drink detox tea before going to bed to cleanse our intestines. It is also recommended that we eat at the same time every day, limit distractions during meals, have pleasant conversations with others, and eat until we are full but not full. This usually involves eating a food called kitchari (meat, mung beans, and spices) at every meal every day to replenish our energy.

Detox Water Health Benefits and Negative Thoughts

We can't speed up or improve our body's detoxification process by drinking detox water.

However, it is still a good drink with some health benefits.

Drink eight glasses of water every day.

Lose weight. Separates the real health benefits from the myths.

It is sometimes called fruit juice or fruitflavored water. We can use any fruit, vegetables and herbs we like. This makes it popular to drink in a detox treatment like Lemon Detox or Detox M aster.

How to Make Detox Water

It's easy to make detox water at home. All we need is water and a variety of fruits, vegetables, and herbs. The more ingredients we use, the stronger the flavor. But be sure to remove the ingredients after this time so they don't start to spoil. Taste quickly.

Here are some popular detox water recipes:

- cucumber and mint
- lemon and ginger
- blackberry and orange
- lemon and cayenne pepper
- watermelon and mint
- grapefruit and rosemary
- orange and lemon
- lemon and lime
- strawberry and basil
- apple and cinnamon

Detox Water Health Claims

Detox water is said to have many health benefits:

- Weight loss
- Detoxification or detoxification
- Balances body pH
- Improves digestive health
- Improves immunity
- Improves mood
- Boosts energy
- Improves skin tone

The properties of detox water will vary depending on the ingredients we use and the strength of the infusion. Most of the health claims of water can be attributed to the water itself rather than its flavoring ingredients. Health benefits the studies behind the health claims of detox water include the following. Some are valid, although exaggerated in some cases. Studies show that water can temporarily increase our metabolic rate, thus burning more calories. In fact, people who drink the recommended amounts of water as part of a weight loss plan lose more weight than those who do not. Water can help we lose weight. . Drinking water is thought to reduce hunger, so if we drink water before a meal with a cleansing and proper diet, we may eat less. Constant thirst can cause constipation, leaving we feel bloated and drunk; it can help food move through the intestines and prevent constipation. Concentration and energy levels. 1.2 liters of

water per day. Therewith be happier, have more energy, and feel calmer when they increase their water intake to 85 ounces (2.5 liters) per day. If we were not drinking enough water, increasing our water intake can improve our mood and make us feel better. More Strength. Yes, regular vitamin C intake has been shown to improve our immune system. But the nutrients we will get from drinking water like detox water may be few and far between. It's theoretically possible, but detox water does not seem to be effective in preventing disease. (Sushruta samhita *et al* 2007)

Fig 1 : Herbs for detoxification

[\(https://rdayurvedicmedicine.com/page/2/\)](https://rdayurvedicmedicine.com/page/2/)

Drinking too much water can impair our judgment and weaken our body. It can take up to 13 hrs for our body to recover from the psychological effects of alcohol, and up to several days for it to completely clear from our system. This decline can affect our metabolism, immunity, and body function. Here are some effective detoxification remedies in Ayurveda:

Kamekh

Kamekh contains phytochemicals that help regulate liver enzymes, promote detoxification, improve hangover symptoms, and provide recovery from alcohol poisoning.

Prepare a decoction by soaking the kamehe plant in water for a few hours. Drinking filtered water can help reduce hangovers. Remember that it tastes bitter; adding honey will help.

However, it is an excellent detoxifying plant. Due to its hepatoprotective properties, neem can be used as a hangover cure as it is suitable for dealing with alcohol and protects our vital organs from the negative effects of alcohol. Grind neem leaves with a mortar and pestle to make a paste. Eat immediately after drinking alcohol as it can cause vomiting. Wait for the "chaos" in our stomach to pass. But it is more than just removing toxins; it is also a powerful force for the mind, calming down stress during stressful times and reducing stress. We can add some leaves to teas

oup or vegetable juice to cure morning hangovers and restore liver function. We survived a very bad situation yesterday.

It is an antiinflammatory drug that is hepatoprotective and also helps with liver function. It helps replenish vital fluids in the body and helps prevent hiccups caused by excessive alcohol consumption. Phyllanthus emblica has excellent detoxification and hepatoprotective properties that come in handy after a night of drinking. Eating amla can help neutralize the negative effects of alcohol on our mind and body. One of the elements. Its main function is to secrete bile to aid digestion. But there is more. This disease affects overall health and can be fatal. Therefore, it is important to love our heart and take good care of it. (Sharma H *et al*)

Carrots

Leaf leaves

Green tea

Citrus fruits

Walnuts

Along with this Ayurvedic medicine for liver cleansing, we can also take Heposem - an herbal medicine to protect and heal the liver and strengthen the liver. (Jonas WB *et al*)

MARKETLY AVAILABLE AYURVEDIC FORMULATIONS

ASAVA and ARISHTA

Name	Source	Uses
Drakshasava	grapes	Anemia, Fatigue, Digestive weakness
Kumaryasava	Aloevera	Liver disorder, Gynaecological issues
Arjunarishta	Arjuna bark	Cardiovascular, Hypertension.
Ashokarishta	Ashoka tree bark	Menstrual Disorders, Uterine Disorders
Dashmoolarishta	Bilva, Agnimantha, Kashmari, Shyonaka, and Patala	Post partum recovery, Inflammatory conditions Joint disorders

CHURNA:

NAME	PRIMARY USE
Vyoshadi Churna	Indigestion, Diarrhea
Panchasakar Churna	Laxative
Mahasudarshan Churna	Fever, Hepatic Detoxification
AjmodadiChurna	Digestive pain
Avipattikar Churna	Acidity, Gastritis
AshwagandhaChurna	Adaptogen, Stress
Udvertana Churna	Body massage,Obesity

CLINICAL USES OF CHURNAS:

NAME	CLINICAL USE
TryushnadiChurna	Significant reduction in body weight, body mass and fasting blood sugar
Jatamansi-moolaChurna	Hypotension, Alleviated insomnia
Arjuna ksheerapakaChurna	Reduces low density lipoprotein (LDL) Reduces total cholesterol Manage glucose with better liver safety
Ashwagandha Churna	Treatment of menopausal syndrome
Vyoshadi Guggulu and Panchasama Churna	Treatment of rheumatoid Arthritis Morning stiffness and joint swelling
VidangadiChurna	Used in obesity management
Shatyadi Churna	Significantly improved allergic rhinitis symptoms
NimbadiChurna	Treatment of gout

LEHYA

NAME	PRIMARY USE
Chyavanaprasha	Immune support, Improve respiratory health
Kantakari Avaleha	Treatment of bronchial asthma, Treatment of chronic cough
Vyaghrihar Avaleha	Treatment of chronic bronchitis
Ashwagandhadi Lehya	Rejuvenation,Strength, Used as Aphrodisiac

CLINICAL USES OF LEHYA

NAME	CLINICAL USES
Kantakari Avaleha and Vasa Avaleha	Used in asthma management by significantly improving respiratory symptoms

Chyavanaprasha Avaleha and Ashwagandhadi Avaleha	Enhances quality of life and Physical performance, Memory enhancement, Reduces depression
Vyaghri haritaki Avaleha	Treatment of atrophic rhinitis
Chitrakaharitaki Avaleha	Treatment of upper respiratory tract infections

GHRITA

NAME	PRIMARY USE
Triphala Ghrita	Boosts immunity, Promotes hair growth, Detoxifies the body, Improves eye health.
S Mahatiktaka Ghrita	Treat skin diseases, Treat bleeding disorders, Treatment of gout, heart diseases and gastritis, Effective in chronic diseases
Brahmi Ghrita	Supports memory, Improves concentration and cognitive health

BHASMA

NAME	PRIMARY USE
Heerak Bhasma	Treatment of cancer, Treatment of certain immunity disorders, Treatment of bone marrow depression
Trailokya Cintamani ras	Used in respiratory tract infection, Treatment of ovarian cysts and uterine fibroids
Mukta pishti	Lowers blood pressure, Treatment of acidity and ulcers, Treatment of various heart disorders

TAILA

NAME	PRIMARY USE
Vibhitakamajjaitailanasya	Improvement in hair colour, Improves scalp health
Arka taila	Improvement in symptoms of otomycosis (fungal infection that affects external auditory canal)

Conclusion:

A full body detox involves sustainable lifestyle and dietary changes to support the body's detoxification process. This is not a quick fix, but a great way to achieve longterm health and wellness. In general, taking too much amma causes symptoms like lethargy, loss of appetite, weakness, constipation, etc. Detoxification is a series of interventions designed to manage intoxication and withdrawal. It represents the removal of toxins from the body of very ill and/or substance addicted patients. Detoxification is designed to reduce the damage done to the body by drug use.

References:

1. Agnivesh, Charak Samhita, R.K Sharma, Bhagwan Dass, First-Edition-Reprint; 2001, Chowkhamha Sanskrit series office, Varanasi.
2. Vagbhata, Astanaga Hridayam, compiled by Dr. Anna oreshwars Kunte, Krishna Ramachandra Shastri Navare: ninth Edition reprint: 2005.

3. Sushruta samhita with Dalhana Nibahandha Sangraha commentary compiled by Acharya Priyavrat Sharma. Ninth edition reprint 2007.
4. Sharma H, Chandola HM, Singh G, Basisht G. Utilization of Ayurveda in health care; an approach for prevention, health promotion and treatment of disease.
5. Jonas WB. Evidence, ethics and the evaluation of global medicine. In. Callahan D, editor.
6. <https://rdayurvedicmedicine.com/page/2>